

New exact solutions for the (3+1)-dimensional breaking soliton equation

Mohammad Taghi Darvishi, Maliheh Najafi and Mohammad Najafi

Abstract—In this work, we obtain some analytic solutions for the (3+1)-dimensional breaking soliton after obtaining its Hirota's bilinear form. Our calculations show that, three-wave method is very easy and straightforward to solve nonlinear partial differential equations.

Keywords—(3+1)-dimensional breaking soliton equation, Hirota's bilinear form.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent years, many kinds of powerful methods have been proposed to find solutions of nonlinear partial differential equations, numerically and/or analytically, e.g., the variational iteration method [1], [2], [3], the homotopy perturbation method [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], parameter expansion method [9], [10], [11], spectral collocation method [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], homotopy analysis method [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], and the Exp-function method [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28].

The (2+1)-dimensional nonlinear breaking soliton equation has the following form

$$u_{xt} - 4u_{xy}u_x - 2u_{xx}u_y - u_{xxx}y = 0, \quad (1)$$

this equation describes the (2+1)-dimensional interaction of the Riemann wave propagated along the y -axis with a long wave propagated along the x -axis [29]. Wazwaz [30] introduced an extension to equation (1) by adding the last three terms with y replaced by z . His work, enables us to establish the following (3+1)-dimensional breaking soliton equation

$$u_{xt} - 4u_x(u_{xy} + u_{xz}) - 2u_{xx}(u_y + u_z) - (u_{xxx}y + u_{xxx}z) = 0, \quad (2)$$

where $u = u(x, y, z, t) : \mathbb{R}_x \times \mathbb{R}_y \times \mathbb{R}_z \times \mathbb{R}_t \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

Recently, Dai et al. [31], suggested the three-wave method for nonlinear evolution equations. The basic idea of this method applies the Painlevé analysis to make a transformation as

$$u = T(f) \quad (3)$$

for some new and unknown function f . Then we use this transformation in a high dimensional nonlinear equation of the general form

$$F(u, u_t, u_x, u_y, u_z, u_{xx}, u_{yy}, u_{zz}, \dots) = 0, \quad (4)$$

M.T. Darvishi, Maliheh Najafi and Mohammad Najafi: Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science, Razi University, Kermanshah 67149, Iran. **e-mail:** darvishimt@yahoo.com, malihe_math87@yahoo.com and m_najafi82@yahoo.com.

where $u = u(x, y, z, t)$ and F is a polynomial of u and its derivatives. By substituting (3) in (4), the first one converts into the Hirota's bilinear form, which it will solve by taking a special form for f and assuming that the obtained Hirota's bilinear form has three-wave solutions, then we can specify the unknown function f . For more details see [31], [32]. In this paper we solve equation (1) by the three-wave method and obtain some exact and new solutions for it.

II. THE (3+1)-DIMENSIONAL BREAKING SOLITON EQUATION

In this section, we investigate explicit formula of solutions of the following (3+1)-dimensional breaking soliton equation

$$u_{xt} - 4u_x(u_{xy} + u_{xz}) - 2u_{xx}(u_y + u_z) - (u_{xxx}y + u_{xxx}z) = 0. \quad (5)$$

To solve this equation we suppose that

$$\theta = y + kz \quad (6)$$

then equation (5) reduces to

$$u_{xt} - 4(k+1)u_xu_{x\theta} - 2(k+1)u_{xx}u_\theta - (k+1)u_{xxx}\theta = 0. \quad (7)$$

To solve equation (7), we introduce a new dependent variable u by

$$u = 2(\ln f)_x \quad (8)$$

where f is an unknown real function which will be determined. Substituting equation (8) into equation (7), we have

$$[2(\ln f)_x]_{xt} - 4(k+1)[2(\ln f)_x]_x [2(\ln f)_x]_{x\theta} - 2(k+1)[2(\ln f)_x]_{xx} [2(\ln f)_x]_\theta - (k+1)[2(\ln f)_x]_{xxx}\theta = 0, \quad (9)$$

which can be integrated once with respect to x to give

$$[2(\ln f)]_{xt} - 3(k+1)[2(\ln f)]_{xx} [2(\ln f)]_{x\theta} - (k+1)[2(\ln f)]_{xxx}\theta + 2\partial_x^{-1}((\ln f)_{xxx}(\ln f)_{x\theta} - (10)$$

$$(\ln f)_{xx}(\ln f)_{x\theta}) = C,$$

where $\partial_x^{-1}\partial_x = 1$. Taking $C = 0$, therefore, equation (10) can be written as

$$(D_x D_t + D_x^3 D_\theta)f \cdot f + 2f^2 \partial_x^{-1}(D_x(\ln f)_{xx} \cdot (\ln f)_{x\theta}) = 0, \quad (11)$$

where the D-operator is defined by

$$D_x^m D_y^k D_z^p D_t^n f(x, y, z, t) \cdot g(x, y, z, t) = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2}\right)^m \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} - \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2}\right)^k \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial z_1} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z_2}\right)^p \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t_1} - \frac{\partial}{\partial t_2}\right)^n [f(x_1, y_1, z_1, t_1)g(x_2, y_2, z_2, t_2)],$$

and the right hand side is computed in

$$x_1 = x_2 = x, y_1 = y_2 = y, z_1 = z_2 = z, t_1 = t_2 = t.$$

We suppose that

$$\partial_x^{-1}(D_x(\ln f)_{xx} \cdot (\ln f)_{x\theta}) = 0, \quad (12)$$

note that to have a correct solution for equation (5) we must consider (12) in our algebraic systems of equations, which that will be our modification from the three-wave method. Therefore, by our assumption, equation (11) reduces to

$$(D_x D_t + D_x^3 D_\theta) f \cdot f = 0. \quad (13)$$

Now we suppose that the solution of equation (11) as

$$f(x, \xi, t) = e^{-\xi_1} + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2) + \delta_2 e^{\xi_1} \quad (14)$$

where

$$\xi_i = a_i x + b_i \theta + c_i t, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (15)$$

and a_i, b_i, c_i, δ_i are some constants to be determined later. Substituting equation (14) into equation (13) and equating all coefficients of $\sin(\xi_2), \cos(\xi_2), \exp(\xi_1)$ and $\exp(-\xi_1)$ to zero, we get the following set of algebraic equation for $a_i, b_i, c_i, \delta_i, (i = 1, 2)$

$$\begin{aligned} &3a_2^2 a_1 b_1 + 3a_1^2 b_2 a_2 - kb_2 a_2^3 + 3ka_1^2 b_2 a_2 + c_1 a_1 \\ &-ka_1^3 b_1 - a_1^3 b_1 - b_2 a_2^3 - a_2 c_2 + 3ka_2^2 a_1 b_1 = 0, \\ &ka_2^3 b_1 + 3b_2 a_2^2 a_1 - 3a_1^2 b_1 a_2 - ka_1^3 b_2 + c_2 a_1 \\ &-3ka_1^2 b_1 a_2 + 3kb_2 a_2^2 a_1 - a_1^3 b_2 + a_2^3 b_1 + c_1 a_2 = 0, \\ &-4k\delta_1^2 a_2^3 b_2 - 4\delta_1^2 a_2^3 b_2 - \delta_1^2 a_2 c_2 - 16ka_1^3 \delta_3 b_1 \\ &-16a_1^3 \delta_3 b_1 + 4c_1 a_1 \delta_3 = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

and from our assumption, that is, from equation (12) we have

$$\begin{aligned} &a_2^4 b_1 - a_1^3 a_2 b_2 - a_2^3 a_1 b_2 + a_2^2 b_1 a_1^2 = 0, \\ &-4a_1^2 a_2^2 b_2 + 4a_1^3 a_2 b_1 + 4a_2^3 b_1 a_1 - 4a_1^4 b_2 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Solving the system of equations (16) and (17) with the aid of Maple, yields the following cases:

A. Case 1:

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= \frac{b_2 a_1}{a_2}, c_1 = \frac{b_2 a_1 (a_1^2 - 3a_2^2)(k+1)}{a_2}, \\ c_2 &= b_2 (a_1^2 - ka_2^2 + 3ka_1^2 - a_2^2), \delta_2 = -\frac{\delta_1^2 a_2^2}{4a_1^2} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

for some arbitrary real constants a_1, a_2, b_2, k and δ_1 . Substitute equations (18) into equation (8) with equation (14), we obtain the solution as

$$f(x, y, z, t) = e^{-\xi_1} + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2) + \delta_2 e^{\xi_1}$$

and

$$u(x, y, z, t) = 2 \frac{-a_1 e^{-\xi_1} - \delta_1 \sin(\xi_2) a_2 + \delta_2 a_1 e^{\xi_1}}{e^{-\xi_1} + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2) + \delta_2 e^{\xi_1}} \quad (19)$$

for

$$\xi_1 = a_1 x + \frac{b_2 a_1 (y+kz)}{a_2} + \frac{b_2 a_1 (-3a_2^2 + ka_1^2 - 3ka_2^2 + a_1^2)t}{a_2},$$

and

$$\xi_2 = a_2 x + b_2 (y + kz) + (3a_1^2 b_2 - kb_2 a_2^2 + 3ka_1^2 b_2 - b_2 a_2^2) t,$$

and

$$\delta_2 = -\frac{\delta_1^2 a_2^2}{4a_1^2}.$$

If $\delta_2 > 0$, then we obtain the exact breather cross-kink solution

$$u(x, y, z, t) = 2 \frac{-2a_1 \sqrt{\delta_2} \sinh(\xi_1 - \beta) - \delta_1 \sin(\xi_2) a_2}{2\sqrt{\delta_2} \cosh(\xi_1 - \beta) + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2)}$$

for

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2} \ln(\delta_2).$$

If $\delta_2 < 0$, then we obtain the exact breather cross-kink solution

$$u(x, y, z, t) = 2 \frac{-2a_1 \sqrt{-\delta_2} \cosh(\xi_1 - \beta) - \delta_1 \sin(\xi_2) a_2}{2\sqrt{-\delta_2} \sinh(\xi_1 - \beta) + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2)}$$

for

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2} \ln(-\delta_2).$$

B. Case 2:

$$a_1 = ia_2, c_2 = 0, b_2 = 0, c_1 = -4a_2^2 b_1 (k+1) \quad (20)$$

for some arbitrary real constants a_2, b_1, k, δ_1 and δ_2 . Substitute equation (20) into equation (8) with equation (14), we obtain the solution as

$$f(x, y, z, t) = e^{-\xi_1} + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2) + \delta_2 e^{\xi_1}$$

and

$$u(x, y, z, t) = 2 \frac{-ia_2 e^{-\xi_1} - \delta_1 \sin(\xi_2) a_2 + i\delta_2 a_2 e^{\xi_1}}{e^{-\xi_1} + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2) + \delta_2 e^{\xi_1}} \quad (21)$$

for

$$\xi_1 = ia_2 x + b_1 (y + kz) - 4a_2^2 b_1 (k+1) t$$

$$\xi_2 = a_2 x.$$

We make the dependent variable transformation in equation (21) as follows

$$a_2 = -i A_2, \quad (22)$$

where A_2 is real. We obtain new form for equation (21) as follows

$$u(x, y, z, t) = 2 \frac{-A_2 e^{-\xi_1^*} + i \delta_1 \sin(\xi_2^*) A_2 + \delta_2 A_2 e^{\xi_1^*}}{e^{-\xi_1^*} + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2^*) + \delta_2 e^{\xi_1^*}} \quad (23)$$

for

$$\xi_1^* = A_2 x + b_1 (y + kz) + 4 A_2^2 b_1 (k + 1) t$$

$$\xi_2^* = -i A_2 x.$$

If $\delta_2 > 0$ then we obtain the exact breather cross-kink solution

$$u(x, y, z, t) = 2 \frac{-2 A_2 \sqrt{\delta_2} \sinh(\xi_1^* - \beta) + i \delta_1 \sin(\xi_2^*) A_2}{2 \sqrt{\delta_2} \cosh(\xi_1^* - \beta) + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2^*)}$$

for

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \ln(\delta_2).$$

If $\delta_2 < 0$ then we obtain the exact breather cross-kink solution

$$u(x, y, z, t) = 2 \frac{-2 A_2 \sqrt{-\delta_2} \cosh(\xi_1^* - \beta) + i \delta_1 \sin(\xi_2^*) A_2}{2 \sqrt{-\delta_2} \sinh(\xi_1^* - \beta) + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2^*)}$$

for

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \ln(-\delta_2).$$

C. Case 3:

$$a_1 = i a_2, b_1 = i b_2, \quad (24)$$

$$c_1 = -i (8 k b_2 a_2^2 + 8 b_2 a_2^2 + c_2), \delta_2 = \frac{\delta_1^2}{4}$$

for some arbitrary real constants a_2, b_2, c_2, k and δ_1 . Substitute equation (24) into equation (8) with equation (14), we obtain the solution as follows

$$f(x, y, z, t) = e^{-\xi_1} + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2) + \delta_2 e^{\xi_1}$$

and

$$u(x, y, z, t) = 2 \frac{-i a_2 e^{-\xi_1} - \delta_1 \sin(\xi_2) a_2 + i \delta_2 a_2 e^{\xi_1}}{e^{-\xi_1} + \delta_1 \cos(\xi_2) + \delta_2 e^{\xi_1}} \quad (25)$$

for

$$\xi_1 = i a_2 x + i b_2 (y + kz) - i (8 k b_2 a_2^2 + 8 b_2 a_2^2 + c_2) t$$

$$\xi_2 = a_2 x + b_2 (y + kz) + c_2 t$$

and

$$\delta_2 = \frac{\delta_1^2}{4}. \quad (26)$$

We make the dependent variable transformation in equation (25) as follows

$$a_2 = i A_2,$$

$$b_2 = i B_2, \quad (27)$$

$$c_2 = i C_2,$$

where A_2, B_2 and C_2 are real. We obtain new form for equation (25) as

$$u(x, y, z, t) = -2 \frac{A_2 (e^{-\xi_1^*} - \delta_1 \sinh(\xi_2^*) - \delta_2 e^{\xi_1^*})}{e^{-\xi_1^*} + \delta_1 \cosh(\xi_2^*) + \delta_2 e^{\xi_1^*}} \quad (28)$$

for

$$\xi_1^* = A_2 x + B_2 y + B_2 k z + (8 B_2 k A_2^2 + 8 B_2 A_2^2 - C_2) t$$

$$\xi_2^* = A_2 x + B_2 y + B_2 k z + C_2 t.$$

If $\delta_2 > 0$ then we obtain the exact breather cross-kink solution

$$u(x, y, z, t) = -2 \frac{A_2 (2 \sqrt{\delta_2} \sinh(\xi_1^* - \beta) - \delta_1 \sinh(\xi_2^*))}{2 \sqrt{\delta_2} \cosh(\xi_1^* - \beta) + \delta_1 \cosh(\xi_2^*)}$$

for

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2} \ln(\delta_2), \quad \delta_2 = \frac{\delta_1^2}{4}.$$

If $\delta_2 < 0$ then we obtain the exact breather cross-kink solution

$$u(x, y, z, t) = -2 \frac{A_2 (2 \sqrt{-\delta_2} \cosh(\xi_1^* - \beta) - \delta_1 \sinh(\xi_2^*))}{2 \sqrt{-\delta_2} \sinh(\xi_1^* - \beta) + \delta_1 \cosh(\xi_2^*)}$$

for

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \ln(-\delta_2), \quad \delta_2 = \frac{\delta_1^2}{4}.$$

III. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we introduced a modification of three-wave method, and we obtained some analytic solutions for the (3+1)-dimensional breaking soliton equation in its bilinear form. We can apply this modification when a PDE does not have a bilinear closed form. By comparison of three-wave method and another analytic methods, like HAM, HTA and EHTA methods, we can see that the new idea is very easy and straightforward which can be applied on another nonlinear partial differential equations.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.H. He, *Variational iteration method-a kind of non-linear analytical technique: some examples*, Int. J. Non-linear Mech. 34(4) (1999) 699–708.
- [2] M.T. Darvishi, F. Khani, A.A. Soliman, *The numerical simulation for stiff systems of ordinary differential equations*, Comput. Math. Appl. 54(7-8) (2007) 1055–1063.
- [3] M.T. Darvishi, F. Khani, *Numerical and explicit solutions of the fifth-order Korteweg-de Vries equations*, Chaos, Solitons and Fractals 39 (2009) 2484–2490.
- [4] J.H. He, *New interpretation of homotopy perturbation method*, Int. J. Mod. Phys. B 20(18) (2006) 2561–2568.
- [5] J.H. He, *Application of homotopy perturbation method to nonlinear wave equations*, Chaos, Solitons and Fractals 26(3) (2005) 695–700.
- [6] J.H. He, *Homotopy perturbation method for bifurcation of nonlinear problems*, Int. J. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simul. 6(2) (2005) 207–208.
- [7] M.T. Darvishi, F. Khani, *Application of He's homotopy perturbation method to stiff systems of ordinary differential equations*, Zeitschrift fur Naturforschung A. 63a (1-2) (2008) 19–23.
- [8] M.T. Darvishi, F. Khani, S. Hamed-Nezhad, S.-W. Ryu, *New modification of the HPM for numerical solutions of the sine-Gordon and coupled sine-Gordon equations*, Int. J. Comput. Math. 87(4) (2010) 908–919.
- [9] J.H. He, *Bookkeeping parameter in perturbation methods*, Int. J. Nonlin. Sci. Numer. Simul. 2 (2001) 257–264.
- [10] M.T. Darvishi, A. Karami, B.-C. Shin, *Application of He's parameter-expansion method for oscillators with smooth odd nonlinearities*, Phys. Lett. A 372(33) (2008) 5381–5384.

- [11] B.-C. Shin, M.T. Darvishi, A. Karami, *Application of He's parameter-expansion method to a nonlinear self-excited oscillator system*, Int. J. Nonlin. Sci. Num. Simul. 10(1) (2009) 137–143.
- [12] M.T. Darvishi, *Preconditioning and domain decomposition schemes to solve PDEs*, Int'l J. of Pure and Applied Math. 1(4) (2004) 419–439.
- [13] M.T. Darvishi, S. Kheybari and F. Khani, *A numerical solution of the Korteweg-de Vries equation by pseudospectral method using Darvishi's preconditionings*, Appl. Math. Comput. 182(1) (2006) 98–105.
- [14] M.T. Darvishi, M. Javidi, *A numerical solution of Burgers' equation by pseudospectral method and Darvishi's preconditioning*, Appl. Math. Comput. 173(1) (2006) 421–429.
- [15] M.T. Darvishi, F. Khani and S. Kheybari, *Spectral collocation solution of a generalized Hirota-Satsuma KdV equation*, Int. J. Comput. Math. 84(4) (2007) 541–551.
- [16] M.T. Darvishi, F. Khani, S. Kheybari, *Spectral collocation method and Darvishi's preconditionings to solve the generalized Burgers-Huxley equation*, Commun., Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simul. 13(10) (2008) 2091–2103.
- [17] S.J. Liao, *An explicit, totally analytic approximate solution for Blasius viscous flow problems*, Int. J. Non-Linear Mech. 34 (1999) 759–778.
- [18] S.J. Liao, *Beyond Perturbation: Introduction to the Homotopy Analysis Method*, Chapman & Hall/CRC Press, Boca Raton, 2003.
- [19] S.J. Liao, *On the homotopy analysis method for nonlinear problems*, Appl. Math. Comput. 147 (2004) 499–513.
- [20] S.J. Liao, *A new branch of solutions of boundary-layer flows over an impermeable stretched plate*, Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer 48 (2005) 2529–2539.
- [21] S.J. Liao, *A general approach to get series solution of non-similarity boundary-layer flows*, Commun. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simul. 14(5) (2009) 2144–2159.
- [22] M.T. Darvishi, F. Khani, *A series solution of the foam drainage equation*, Comput. Math. Appl. 58 (2009) 360–368.
- [23] J.H. He, M.A. Abdou, *New periodic solutions for nonlinear evolution equations using Exp-function method*, Chaos, Solitons and Fractals 34 (2007) 1421–1429.
- [24] J.H. He, X.H. Wu, *Exp-function method for nonlinear wave equations*, Chaos, Solitons and Fractals, 30(3) (2006) 700–708.
- [25] J.H. He, X.H. Wu, *Construction of solitary solution and compacton-like solution by variational iteration method*, Chaos, Solitons and Fractals, 29 (2006) 108–113.
- [26] F. Khani, S. Hamed-Nezhad, M.T. Darvishi, S.-W. Ryu, *New solitary wave and periodic solutions of the foam drainage equation using the Exp-function method*, Nonlin. Anal.: Real World Appl. 10 (2009) 1904–1911.
- [27] B.-C. Shin, M.T. Darvishi, A. Barati, *Some exact and new solutions of the Nizhnik-Novikov-Vesselov equation using the Exp-function method*, Comput. Math. Appl. 58(11/12) (2009) 2147–2151.
- [28] X.H. Wu, J.H. He, *Exp-function method and its application to nonlinear equations*, Chaos, Solitons and Fractals 38(3) (2008) 903–910.
- [29] S.-H. Ma, J. Peng, C. Zhang, *New exact solutions of the (2+1)-dimensional breaking soliton system via an extended mapping method*, Chaos Solitons Fractals, 46 (2009) 210–214.
- [30] A.M. Wazwaz, *Integrable (2+1)-dimensional and (3+1)-dimensional breaking soliton equations*, Phys. Scr., 81 (2010) 1–5.
- [31] Z.D. Dai, S.Q. Lin, D.L. Li, G. Mu, *The three-wave method for nonlinear evaluation equations*, Nonl. Sci. Lett. A, 1(1) (2010) 77–82.
- [32] C.J. Wang, Z.D. Dai, L. Liang, *Exact three-wave solution for higher dimensional KDV-type equation*, Appl. Math. Comput., 216 (2010) 501–505.